

Fixed Point Theorems of Two-Step Iterations for Generalized Z -Type Condition in $CAT(0)$ Spaces

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Abstract: In this paper, we establish some strong convergence theorems of modified two-step iterations for generalized Z -type condition in the setting of $CAT(0)$ spaces. Our results extend and improve the corresponding results of [3, 6, 28] and many others from the current existing literature.

Key Words: Strong convergence, modified two-step iteration scheme, fixed point, $CAT(0)$ space.

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§1. Introduction

A metric space X is a $CAT(0)$ space if it is geodesically connected and if every geodesic triangle in X is at least as ‘thin’ as its comparison triangle in the Euclidean plane. It is well known that any complete, simply connected Riemannian manifold having non-positive sectional curvature is a $CAT(0)$ space. Fixed point theory in a $CAT(0)$ space was first studied by Kirk (see [19, 20]). He showed that every nonexpansive (single-valued) mapping defined on a bounded closed convex subset of a complete $CAT(0)$ space always has a fixed point. Since, then the fixed point theory for single-valued and multi-valued mappings in $CAT(0)$ spaces has been rapidly developed, and many papers have appeared (see, e.g., [2], [9], [11]-[13], [17]-[18], [21]-[22], [24]-[26] and references therein). It is worth mentioning that the results in $CAT(0)$ spaces can be applied to any $CAT(k)$ space with $k \leq 0$ since any $CAT(k)$ space is a $CAT(m)$ space for every $m \geq k$ (see [7]).

Let (X, d) be a metric space. A *geodesic path* joining $x \in X$ to $y \in X$ (or, more briefly, a geodesic from x to y) is a map c from a closed interval $[0, l] \subset \mathbb{R}$ to X such that $c(0) = x$, $c(l) = y$ and $d(c(t), c(t')) = |t - t'|$ for all $t, t' \in [0, l]$. In particular, c is an isometry, and $d(x, y) = l$. The image α of c is called a geodesic (or metric) *segment* joining x and y . We say X is (i) a *geodesic space* if any two points of X are joined by a geodesic and (ii) a *uniquely geodesic* if there is exactly one geodesic joining x and y for each $x, y \in X$, which we will denote by $[x, y]$, called the segment joining x to y .

A *geodesic triangle* $\Delta(x_1, x_2, x_3)$ in a geodesic metric space (X, d) consists of three points

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in X (the vertices of Δ) and a geodesic segment between each pair of vertices (the *edges* of Δ). A *comparison triangle* for geodesic triangle $\Delta(x_1, x_2, x_3)$ in (X, d) is a triangle $\overline{\Delta}(x_1, x_2, x_3) := \Delta(\overline{x}_1, \overline{x}_2, \overline{x}_3)$ in \mathbb{R}^2 such that $d_{\mathbb{R}^2}(\overline{x}_i, \overline{x}_j) = d(x_i, x_j)$ for $i, j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$. Such a triangle always exists (see [7]).

1.1 CAT(0) Space

A geodesic metric space is said to be a $CAT(0)$ space if all geodesic triangles of appropriate size satisfy the following $CAT(0)$ comparison axiom.

Let Δ be a geodesic triangle in X , and let $\overline{\Delta} \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ be a comparison triangle for Δ . Then Δ is said to satisfy the $CAT(0)$ inequality if for all $x, y \in \Delta$ and all comparison points $\overline{x}, \overline{y} \in \overline{\Delta}$,

$$d(x, y) \leq d_{\mathbb{R}^2}(\overline{x}, \overline{y}). \quad (1.1)$$

Complete $CAT(0)$ spaces are often called *Hadamard spaces* (see [16]). If x, y_1, y_2 are points of a $CAT(0)$ space and y_0 is the mid point of the segment $[y_1, y_2]$ which we will denote by $(y_1 \oplus y_2)/2$, then the $CAT(0)$ inequality implies

$$d^2\left(x, \frac{y_1 \oplus y_2}{2}\right) \leq \frac{1}{2} d^2(x, y_1) + \frac{1}{2} d^2(x, y_2) - \frac{1}{4} d^2(y_1, y_2). \quad (1.2)$$

The inequality (1.2) is the (CN) inequality of Bruhat and Tits [8]. The above inequality was extended in [12] as

$$\begin{aligned} d^2(z, \alpha x \oplus (1 - \alpha)y) &\leq \alpha d^2(z, x) + (1 - \alpha)d^2(z, y) \\ &\quad - \alpha(1 - \alpha)d^2(x, y) \end{aligned} \quad (1.3)$$

for any $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ and $x, y, z \in X$.

Let us recall that a geodesic metric space is a $CAT(0)$ space if and only if it satisfies the (CN) inequality (see [7, page 163]). Moreover, if X is a $CAT(0)$ metric space and $x, y \in X$, then for any $\alpha \in [0, 1]$, there exists a unique point $\alpha x \oplus (1 - \alpha)y \in [x, y]$ such that

$$d(z, \alpha x \oplus (1 - \alpha)y) \leq \alpha d(z, x) + (1 - \alpha)d(z, y), \quad (1.4)$$

for any $z \in X$ and $[x, y] = \{\alpha x \oplus (1 - \alpha)y : \alpha \in [0, 1]\}$.

A subset C of a $CAT(0)$ space X is convex if for any $x, y \in C$, we have $[x, y] \subset C$.

We recall the following definitions in a metric space (X, d) . A mapping $T: X \rightarrow X$ is called an a -contraction if

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq a d(x, y) \text{ for all } x, y \in X, \quad (1.5)$$

where $a \in (0, 1)$.

The mapping T is called Kannan mapping [15] if there exists $b \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ such that

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq b [d(x, Tx) + d(y, Ty)] \quad (1.6)$$

for all $x, y \in X$.

The mapping T is called Chatterjea mapping [10] if there exists $c \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ such that

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq c [d(x, Ty) + d(y, Tx)] \quad (1.7)$$

for all $x, y \in X$.

In 1972, Zamfirescu [29] proved the following important result.

Theorem Z *Let (X, d) be a complete metric space and $T: X \rightarrow X$ a mapping for which there exists the real number a, b and c satisfying $a \in (0, 1)$, $b, c \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ such that for any pair $x, y \in X$, at least one of the following conditions holds:*

- (z₁) $d(Tx, Ty) \leq a d(x, y)$;
- (z₂) $d(Tx, Ty) \leq b [d(x, Tx) + d(y, Ty)]$;
- (z₃) $d(Tx, Ty) \leq c [d(x, Ty) + d(y, Tx)]$.

Then T has a unique fixed point p and the Picard iteration $\{x_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ defined by

$$x_{n+1} = Tx_n, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

converges to p for any arbitrary but fixed $x_0 \in X$.

An operator T which satisfies at least one of the contractive conditions (z₁), (z₂) and (z₃) is called a *Zamfirescu operator* or a *Z-operator*.

In 2004, Berinde [5] proved the strong convergence of Ishikawa iterative process defined by: for $x_0 \in C$, the sequence $\{x_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ given by

$$\begin{aligned} x_{n+1} &= (1 - \alpha_n)x_n + \alpha_n T y_n, \\ y_n &= (1 - \beta_n)x_n + \beta_n T x_n, \quad n \geq 0, \end{aligned} \quad (1.8)$$

to approximate fixed points of Zamfirescu operator in an arbitrary Banach space E . While proving the theorem, he made use of the condition,

$$\|Tx - Ty\| \leq \delta \|x - y\| + 2\delta \|x - Tx\| \quad (1.9)$$

which holds for any $x, y \in E$ where $0 \leq \delta < 1$.

In 1953, W.R. Mann defined the Mann iteration [23] as

$$u_{n+1} = (1 - a_n)u_n + a_n T u_n, \quad (1.10)$$

where $\{a_n\}$ is a sequence of positive numbers in $[0, 1]$.

In 1974, S.Ishikawa defined the Ishikawa iteration [14] as

$$\begin{aligned} s_{n+1} &= (1 - a_n)s_n + a_n T t_n, \\ t_n &= (1 - b_n)s_n + b_n T s_n, \end{aligned} \quad (1.11)$$

where $\{a_n\}$ and $\{b_n\}$ are sequences of positive numbers in $[0, 1]$.

In 2008, S.Thianwan defined the new two step iteration [27] as

$$\begin{aligned}\nu_{n+1} &= (1 - a_n)w_n + a_n T w_n, \\ w_n &= (1 - b_n)\nu_n + b_n T \nu_n,\end{aligned}\tag{1.12}$$

where $\{a_n\}$ and $\{b_n\}$ are sequences of positive numbers in $[0,1]$.

Recently, Agarwal et al. [1] introduced the S -iteration process defined as

$$\begin{aligned}x_{n+1} &= (1 - a_n)T x_n + a_n T y_n, \\ y_n &= (1 - b_n)x_n + b_n T x_n,\end{aligned}\tag{1.13}$$

where $\{a_n\}$ and $\{b_n\}$ are sequences of positive numbers in $(0,1)$.

In this paper, inspired and motivated [5, 29], we employ a condition introduced in [6] which is more general than condition (1.9) and establish fixed point theorems of S - iteration scheme in the framework of CAT(0) spaces. The condition is defined as follows:

Let C be a nonempty, closed, convex subset of a CAT(0) space X and $T: C \rightarrow C$ a self map of C . There exists a constant $L \geq 0$ such that for all $x, y \in C$, we have

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq e^{L d(x, Tx)} \left[\delta d(x, y) + 2\delta d(x, Tx) \right],\tag{1.14}$$

where $0 \leq \delta < 1$ and e^x denotes the exponential function of $x \in C$. Throughout this paper, we call this condition as generalized Z -type condition.

Remark 1.1 If $L = 0$, in the above condition, we obtain

$$d(Tx, Ty) \leq \delta d(x, y) + 2\delta d(x, Tx),$$

which is the Zamfirescu condition used by Berinde [5] where

$$\delta = \max \left\{ a, \frac{b}{1-b}, \frac{c}{1-c} \right\}, \quad 0 \leq \delta < 1,$$

while constants a , b and c are as defined in Theorem Z .

Example 1.2 Let X be the real line with the usual norm $\|\cdot\|$ and suppose $C = [0, 1]$. Define $T: C \rightarrow C$ by $Tx = \frac{x+1}{2}$ for all $x, y \in C$. Obviously T is self-mapping with a unique fixed point 1. Now we check that condition (1.14) is true. If $x, y \in [0, 1]$, then $\|Tx - Ty\| \leq e^{L \|x - Tx\|} [\delta \|x - y\| + 2\delta \|x - Tx\|]$ where $0 \leq \delta < 1$. In fact

$$\|Tx - Ty\| = \left\| \frac{x - y}{2} \right\|$$

and

$$e^{L \|x - Tx\|} [\delta \|x - y\| + 2\delta \|x - Tx\|] = e^{L \left\| \frac{x-1}{2} \right\|} [\delta \|x - y\| + \delta \|x - 1\|].$$

Clearly, if we chose $x = 0$ and $y = 1$, then contractive condition (??) is satisfied since

$$\|Tx - Ty\| = \left\| \frac{x - y}{2} \right\| = \frac{1}{2},$$

and for $L \geq 0$, we chose $L = 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned} e^{L\|x-Tx\|} \left[\delta \|x - y\| + 2\delta \|x - Tx\| \right] &= e^{L\|\frac{x-1}{2}\|} \left[\delta \|x - y\| + \delta \|x - 1\| \right] \\ &= e^{0(1/2)}(2\delta) = 2\delta, \quad \text{where } 0 < \delta < 1. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\|Tx - Ty\| \leq e^{L\|x-Tx\|} \left[\delta \|x - y\| + 2\delta \|x - Tx\| \right].$$

Hence T is a self mapping with unique fixed point satisfying the contractive condition (1.14).

Example 1.3 Let X be the real line with the usual norm $\|\cdot\|$ and suppose $K = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$. Define $T: K \rightarrow K$ by

$$\begin{cases} Tx = 2, & \text{if } x = 0 \\ = 3, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Let us take $x = 0$, $y = 1$ and $L = 0$. Then from condition (1.14), we have

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &\leq e^{0(2)}[\delta(1) + 2\delta(2)] \\ &\leq 1(5\delta) = 5\delta \end{aligned}$$

which implies $\delta \geq \frac{1}{5}$. Now if we take $0 < \delta < 1$, then condition (1.14) is satisfied and 3 is of course a unique fixed point of T .

1.2 Modified Two-Step Iteration Schemes in CAT(0) Space

Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of a complete CAT(0) space X . Let $T: C \rightarrow C$ be a contractive operator. Then for a given $x_1 = x_0 \in C$, compute the sequence $\{x_n\}$ by the iterative scheme as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} x_{n+1} &= (1 - a_n)Tx_n \oplus a_nTy_n, \\ y_n &= (1 - b_n)x_n \oplus b_nTx_n, \end{aligned} \tag{1.15}$$

where $\{a_n\}$ and $\{b_n\}$ are sequences of positive numbers in $(0,1)$. Iteration scheme (1.15) is called modified S -iteration scheme in CAT(0) space.

$$\begin{aligned} \nu_{n+1} &= (1 - a_n)w_n \oplus a_nTw_n, \\ w_n &= (1 - b_n)\nu_n \oplus b_nT\nu_n, \end{aligned} \tag{1.16}$$

where $\{a_n\}$ and $\{b_n\}$ are sequences of positive numbers in $[0,1]$. Iteration scheme (1.16) is called

modified S.Thianwan iteration scheme in CAT(0) space.

$$\begin{aligned} s_{n+1} &= (1 - a_n)s_n \oplus a_n T t_n, \\ t_n &= (1 - b_n)s_n \oplus b_n T s_n, \end{aligned} \tag{1.17}$$

where $\{a_n\}$ and $\{b_n\}$ are sequences of positive numbers in $[0,1]$. Iteration scheme (1.17) is called modified Ishikawa iteration scheme in CAT(0) space.

We need the following useful lemmas to prove our main results in this paper.

Lemma 1.4([24]) *Let X be a CAT(0) space.*

(i) *For $x, y \in X$ and $t \in [0, 1]$, there exists a unique point $z \in [x, y]$ such that*

$$d(x, z) = t d(x, y) \text{ and } d(y, z) = (1 - t) d(x, y). \tag{A}$$

We use the notation $(1 - t)x \oplus ty$ for the unique point z satisfying (A).

(ii) *For $x, y \in X$ and $t \in [0, 1]$, we have*

$$d((1 - t)x \oplus ty, z) \leq (1 - t)d(x, z) + td(y, z).$$

Lemma 1.5([4]) *Let $\{p_n\}_{n=0}^\infty, \{q_n\}_{n=0}^\infty, \{r_n\}_{n=0}^\infty$ be sequences of nonnegative numbers satisfying the following condition:*

$$p_{n+1} \leq (1 - s_n)p_n + q_n + r_n, \quad \forall n \geq 0,$$

where $\{s_n\}_{n=0}^\infty \subset [0, 1]$. If $\sum_{n=0}^\infty s_n = \infty$, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} q_n = O(s_n)$ and $\sum_{n=0}^\infty r_n < \infty$, then $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} p_n = 0$.

§2. Strong Convergence Theorems in CAT(0) Space

In this section, we establish some strong convergence theorems of modified two-step iterations to converge to a fixed point of generalized Z-type condition in the framework of CAT(0) spaces.

Theorem 2.1 *Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of a complete CAT(0) space X and let $T: C \rightarrow C$ be a self mapping satisfying generalized Z-type condition given by (1.14) with $F(T) \neq \emptyset$. For any $x_0 \in C$, let $\{x_n\}_{n=0}^\infty$ be the sequence defined by (1.15). If $\sum_{n=0}^\infty a_n = \infty$ and $\sum_{n=0}^\infty a_n b_n = \infty$, then $\{x_n\}_{n=0}^\infty$ converges strongly to the unique fixed point of T .*

Proof From the assumption $F(T) \neq \emptyset$, it follows that T has a fixed point in C , say u . Since T satisfies generalized Z-type condition given by (1.14), then from (1.14), taking $x = u$

and $y = x_n$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} d(Tu, Tx_n) &\leq e^{L d(u, Tu)} \left(\delta d(u, x_n) + 2\delta d(u, Tu) \right) \\ &= e^{L d(u, u)} \left(\delta d(u, x_n) + 2\delta d(u, u) \right) \\ &= e^{L(0)} \left(\delta d(u, x_n) + 2\delta(0) \right), \end{aligned}$$

which implies that

$$d(Tx_n, u) \leq \delta d(x_n, u). \quad (2.1)$$

Similarly by taking $x = u$ and $y = y_n$ in (1.14), we have

$$d(Ty_n, u) \leq \delta d(y_n, u), \quad (2.2)$$

Now using (1.15), (2.2) and Lemma 1.4(ii), we have

$$\begin{aligned} d(y_n, u) &= d((1 - b_n)x_n \oplus b_nTx_n, u) \\ &\leq (1 - b_n)d(x_n, u) + b_n d(Tx_n, u) \\ &\leq (1 - b_n)d(x_n, u) + b_n\delta d(x_n, u) \\ &= (1 - b_n + b_n\delta)d(x_n, u). \end{aligned} \quad (2.3)$$

Now using (1.15), (2.1), (2.3) and Lemma 1.4(ii), we have

$$\begin{aligned} d(x_{n+1}, u) &= d((1 - a_n)Tx_n \oplus a_nTy_n, u) \\ &\leq (1 - a_n)d(Tx_n, u) + a_n d(Ty_n, u) \\ &\leq (1 - a_n)\delta d(x_n, u) + a_n\delta d(y_n, u) \\ &\leq (1 - a_n + a_n\delta)d(x_n, u) + a_n\delta(1 - b_n + b_n\delta)d(x_n, u) \\ &= [1 - (1 - \delta)a_n]d(x_n, u) + a_n\delta[1 - (1 - \delta)b_n]d(x_n, u) \\ &= [1 - (1 - \delta)a_n + a_n\delta(1 - (1 - \delta)b_n)]d(x_n, u) \\ &= [1 - \{(1 - \delta)a_n + \delta(1 - \delta)a_nb_n\}]d(x_n, u) = (1 - \mu_n)d(x_n, u) \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

where $\mu_n = (1 - \delta)a_n + \delta(1 - \delta)a_nb_n$. Since $0 \leq \delta < 1$; $a_n, b_n \in (0, 1)$; $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n = \infty$ and $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_nb_n = \infty$, it follows that $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \mu_n = \infty$. Setting $p_n = d(x_n, u)$, $s_n = \mu_n$ and by applying Lemma 1.5, it follows that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(x_n, u) = 0$. Thus $\{x_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ converges strongly to a fixed point of T .

To show uniqueness of the fixed point u , assume that $u_1, u_2 \in F(T)$ and $u_1 \neq u_2$. Applying generalized Z -type condition given by (1.14) and using the fact that $0 \leq \delta < 1$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} d(u_1, u_2) &= d(Tu_1, Tu_2) \\ &\leq e^{L d(u_1, Tu_1)} \left\{ \delta d(u_1, u_2) + 2\delta d(u_1, Tu_1) \right\} \\ &= e^{L d(u_1, u_1)} \left\{ \delta d(u_1, u_2) + 2\delta d(u_1, u_1) \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= e^{L(0)} \left\{ \delta d(u_1, u_2) + 2\delta(0) \right\} \\
&= \delta d(u_1, u_2) < d(u_1, u_2),
\end{aligned}$$

which is a contradiction. Therefore $u_1 = u_2$. Thus $\{x_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ converges strongly to the unique fixed point of T . \square

Theorem 2.2 *Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of a complete CAT(0) space X and let $T: C \rightarrow C$ be a self mapping satisfying generalized Z-type condition given by (1.14) with $F(T) \neq \emptyset$. For any $x_0 \in C$, let $\{x_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ be the sequence defined by (1.16). If $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n = \infty$, then $\{x_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ converges strongly to the unique fixed point of T .*

Proof The proof of Theorem 2.2 is similar to that of Theorem 2.1. \square

Theorem 2.3 *Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of a complete CAT(0) space X and let $T: C \rightarrow C$ be a self mapping satisfying generalized Z-type condition given by (1.14) with $F(T) \neq \emptyset$. For any $x_0 \in C$, let $\{x_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ be the sequence defined by (1.17). If $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n = \infty$ and $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n b_n = \infty$, then $\{x_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ converges strongly to the unique fixed point of T .*

Proof The proof of Theorem 2.3 is also similar to that of Theorem 2.1. \square

If we take $L = 0$ in condition (1.14), then we obtain the following result as corollary which extends the corresponding result of Berinde [5] to the case of modified S -iteration scheme and from arbitrary Banach space to the setting of CAT(0) spaces.

Corollary 2.4 *Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of a complete CAT(0) space X and let $T: C \rightarrow C$ a Zamfirescu operator. For any $x_0 \in C$, let $\{x_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ be the sequence defined by (1.15). If $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n = \infty$ and $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n b_n = \infty$, then $\{x_n\}$ converges strongly to the unique fixed point of T .*

Remark 2.5 Our results extend and improve upon, among others, the corresponding results proved by Berinde [3], Yildirim et al. [28] and Bosede [6] to the case of generalized Z-type condition, modified S -iteration scheme and from Banach space or normed linear space to the setting of CAT(0) spaces.

§3. Conclusion

The generalized Z-type condition is more general than Zamfirescu operators. Thus the results obtained in this paper are improvement and generalization of several known results in the existing literature (see, e.g., [3, 6, 28] and some others).

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